

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Maruyama****FIRST NAME: Nobutaka****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: (Word for Mac 16.38 on macOS 10.15.5)

INTRODUCTION OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This is my first response paper submitting to Euclid University. I learned about the meaning of writing, especially in academic paper and also how to write it. I would like to record here what I have learned. The first one is about the meaning of writing; the second one is referencing -- the system for academic knowledge integration, and the last one is how to write academic papers practically and efficiently.

2) THE MEANING OF WRITING

The first question to me in this period was "why people write," especially in the academic field. We write, for example, a conference minutes to companies, survey report to institutions, design plan to customers, and sometimes write letters to my family or friends. What is the difference between these and the academic writing?

To this question, now I can say the academic paper has ideas or arguments to specific questions or issues, supported by evidence. The coursepack state very clearly: "An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence" (EUCLID 2019, 1). In Write Source 2000, the recommended book for reference mentioned in the Coursepack, I found memorable lines. I would like to quote below:

"Writing is the ultimate learning tool for all students of all ages in all subjects"

"Write to Explore Your Personal Thoughts"

"Write to Better Understand New Ideas"

"Write to Show Learning"

"Write to Share" (Kemper, Sebranek, and Meyer 1999, 1)

I found another interesting idea, which was about portfolios. In the reference book of this period, the "Write Source 2000", the portfolios were explained as below:

"Many professional people, including writers, artists, and designers, compile portfolios to showcase their talents. A portfolio, in a way, speaks for the person. It says, "This is who I am; this is what I can do." A portfolio also helps potential employers and clients evaluate an individual's talents" (Kemper, Sebranek, and Meyer 1999, 32).

I felt it is an interesting point because, in Japan, the country where I grew up, we do not have these expressing culture generally. People work as a team, do not emphasize an individual. I have heard the word portfolio only in the architecture field, but now I understand what it is meant in western countries. In the course of my study, the way of thinking for a portfolio is useful in terms of organizing what you will think and write. I have felt that the rule of academic writing is rigorous, but I came to understand its background. Furthermore, I am aware again, that the question- "what do you think about individuals or individuals belonging to an organization?" is always cultural controversy as well.

3) REFERENCING – THE ACADEMIC KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION SYSTEM

I understand the almost all academic writings build on pioneers of each field. If we start to study something, you should start with research well these outputs made by the pioneers. Integrating these works of pioneers, you can place your study ideas in the rule of citation, or in other words referencing styles. These are a complicated process, but we can use technology such as word processor works on the computer, or a reference management software like Zotero nowadays.

a) Referencing style

There are many kinds of writing rules in each journal or magazine. The most used one is the so-called Turabian style. This is Chicago style, but the reference manual writer's name "Turabian" is well used for showing him our respect.

i) In-text citations

In-text citations is the shortest version to explain the references that you cited. Usually, write reference authors' names and citing pages into parentheses, and put just after the lines (EUCLID 2019, 5–6).

ii) *Quotations*

If you want to use the words or lines directly, quote the words or lines making any changes, among the quotation marks. You have to show reference in the same way as i) (EUCLID 2019, 6–8).

iii) *Paraphrasing*

It is advisable to cite the ideas in your own words, because sometimes if all lines are citations, it is annoying to our readers. If you use this way, you should read the material thoroughly, and write your own words to express the author's idea. The important thing is not to be similar to the original writing style as well as wordings. Furthermore, you also need to put references for the referring lines even if you make it all in your words (EUCLID 2019, 8–9).

4) **HOW TO WRITE ACADEMIC PAPERS**

When you write academic papers, an efficient way is listed below. The procedure is explained clearly in the coursebook for this period (EUCLID 2019, 1–4).

a) Have questions, hypothesis

Academic papers should have ideas to raised issues. Therefore, what you should do first for writing an academic paper is to grasp issues or questions. Any academic papers must have an argument; all readers hope the writing argues something (EUCLID 2019, 1).

b) Do research, read materials

The academic paper must have ideas or arguments to specific questions or issues, supported by evidence. Therefore, you have to read relevant documents as much as possible before constructing your ideas. Through these activities, you can find supporting ideas to prove your arguments. Then your reader will also trace the background of the argument easily (EUCLID 2019, 2).

c) Construct well to deliver

Before to start writing, you should think about construction. You should make "Essay Plan," your paper should have an introduction, main points, and conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 1–3).

d) Start to write early

You should start writing as early as possible. Writing academic papers needs much time for thinking about construction, proofreading, or procedure for publishing. If you start early, more you will be able to obtain reflecting time for your revision. That makes your writing ideas deliver well to the readers (EUCLID 2019, 1–4).

e) Revise repeatedly

After writing the draft of papers, it is a smart way to leave it several days before reviewing it. With a fresh perspective, you can easily find, such as your logical flow or misspells. The useful checklist also provided by EUCLID (EUCLID 2019, 4).

5) CONCLUSION

Writing essays or papers are no easy task, but written materials can be seen by many people who are interested in the same study theme as yourself. Once the ideas would be written down, it can connect next someone's idea pieces, and that makes a new value proposition in the world. In this sense, academic writing is an exciting challenge for the advancement of our culture or society. Lastly, I must acknowledge the main text of this period again, which patiently encourages us this writing exploration. I am sincerely appreciative of the authors of the text.

REFERENCES

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Kemper, Dave, Patrick Sebranek, and Verne Meyer. 1999. *Write Source: Skills Book Teacher's Edition Grade 6*. 4th ed. Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group Inc.

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